

Grant Agreement Number: 957204 (H2020-ICT-38-2020)
Project Acronym: MAS4AI
Project Start Date: 1st October 2020
Project Full Title: Multi-Agent Systems for Pervasive Artificial Intelligence for assisting Humans in Modular Production

D1.3 – Intelligent Multi-agent System Architecture

Dissemination level:	PU
Date:	2021-01-12
Deliverable leader:	DFKI
Contributors:	TNO, LMS, TECNALIA, AIMEN, SCM, SEMAKU, CASP, FLEXIS, SIS, DMD, VW
Reviewers:	LMS
Type:	R
WP / Task responsible:	DFKI
Keywords:	System Architecture, RAMI4.0

Executive Summary

This document consists the deliverable D1.3, which describes the MAS4AI architecture that serves as the foundation for future work in the project. The architecture is synchronized with the reference architecture for Industry 4.0 (RAMI4.0) and considers other generic digital reference architectures. Furthermore, design principles for the MAS architecture in the manufacturing domain are given.

In order to make the MAS4AI MAS architecture applicable to a large variety of manufacturing scenarios, it uses the concept of Holons as an abstraction to group multiple agents and to coordinate both control and information flow. This is formulated to be compatible with the definition of Industry 4.0 components. Also, it presents the concept of an Agent service description (ASD), which serves as an abstraction element between agents and the asset information shell of a holon. Also, additional information about machine learning (ML) capabilities and cloud connectors for the agents are given

The document is structured in the following way. Section 2 gives a general overview of the selected reference architectures, which are worth to be considered in the MAS4AI project. Section 3 describes the MAS4AI high level structure. In section 4 the conceptual design of the MAS4AI architecture and the main design principals are discussed. After the description of the basic concept of the holon and its creation, information about used protocols and interaction patterns are given. The aim is to use generic I4.0 communication protocols for the communication and interaction between agents, holons and other assets. Section 5 gives the formal description of the MAS4AI reference architecture using the UML notation. In section 6 further steps, the components and utilized frameworks of the proposed architecture are developed and prototypically implemented in the test facilities. Section 7 concludes the deliverable.

Document History			
Version	Date	Contributors	Description
V01	2021-02-20	DFKI	Initial Version of the document
V02	2021-03-28	DFKI	Integration first draft architecture
V03	2021-04-21	DFKI	Consolidated changes
V04	2022-03-31	DFKI	Updated version

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1 Introduction

In computer science, reference architectures describe software architectures that reflect the corresponding elements and relationships between the elements in a system and can be used as templates for further use and implementation. These are usually domain-specific due to the special requirements of the respective area of application. Typical components of such an architecture are common data models, communication and exchange standards, and sometimes reusable templates and software building blocks.

The manufacturing sector is a particularly demanding domain. Factories usually form very complex structures that are mostly hierarchically structured and form a wide, heterogeneous landscape from hardware-related programmable control units to cloud-based ERP systems. This wide range and the high degree of individualised software and hardware pose special challenges for the systems used in them. In order to make such complex systems controllable and to be able to quickly apply new AI-based technologies in them, multi-agent-based systems are proposed. These are particularly characterised by their ability to solve complex computational problems efficiently.

This document describes a reference architecture to be able to use such multi-agent systems with AI capabilities in a generic manufacturing environment. It is important to consider already existing reference architectures of the manufacturing environment, such as the reference architecture for industry 4.0 (RAMI4.0). In addition, other generic digital reference architectures are explained and taken into account for the creation of the MAS4AI reference architecture.

In order to make the MAS4AI MAS architecture applicable to a variety of manufacturing scenarios, it uses the concept of Holons as an abstraction to group multiple agents and to coordinate both control and information flow. This is formulated to be compatible with the definition of Industry 4.0 components. Also, it presents the concept of an Agent service description (ASD), which serves as an abstraction element between agents and the asset information shell of a holon. Also, additional information about machine learning (ML) capabilities and cloud connectors for the agents are given.

After the description of the basic concept of the holon and its creation, information about used protocols and interaction patterns are given. The aim is to use generic I4.0 communication protocols for the communication and interaction between agents, holons and other assets.

In further steps, the components and utilized frameworks of the proposed architecture are developed and prototypically implemented in the test facilities.

2 Overview of generic reference architectures

This section gives an overview of generic reference architectures as a thematic framework for the development of the MAS4AI Multiagent system.

2.1 Rami 4.0

Figure 1 RAMI 4.0 Architecture

The overall MAS4AI system architecture which supports the development and deployment of multi-agent-based AI applications for autonomous modular production will be developed in this task. The holistic system architecture will take as a basis the Reference Architecture Model Industry 4.0 (RAMI 4.0), shown in Figure 1, for deploying AI services on different hierarchical levels (module level, factory level and enterprise level). Both domain-specific (i.e., Business Services) and non-domain-specific Services (i.e., Infrastructure Services, Management Services, Middleware etc) and components will be determined, considering existing enterprise applications (i.e., legacy systems) and/or new services components that might be needed to meet the system requirements and the project technical objectives. This task will therefore include an extended set of architectural elements and relations associated with the production processes and to the involved production modules, providing a seamless and secure vertical and horizontal

integration considering the most recent releases of relevant and generic reference architectures for digital industries.

Axis 1: Product life cycle

The life cycle of assets in RAMI is represented within axis “Life Cycle Value Stream”, based on the value-stream standard IEC 62890. This standard describes the basic principles for the life cycle management of systems. An important differentiation at this axis is made between the “Type” and the “Instance” of an asset in RAMI. An asset in the stage of “Type” can become an asset of “Instance”. This categorization follows the parts “Development” and “Production” of an asset which is necessary for manufacturing. This differentiation can also be done for the maintenance-related part of an asset, also following the classification of “Type” and “Instance”.

Axis 2: Hierarchy Levels

“Hierarchy Levels” of RAMI follows standard IEC 62242. This standard describes IT integration companies and control systems. These hierarchy levels represent the different functionalities that are related to a factory or plant and. The levels “Product” and “Connected World” are added to the standard IEC 62242. “Connected World” represents the connectivity of an asset in RAMI with other IoT components. This includes a connected environment but also each IoT-based object can be considered in this model to interact with a digitalized and connected factory.

Axis 3: Layers

The axis “Layers” of RAMI structures an asset representation in a digital way. These layers are related to information and communication technology and are integrated into RAMI. These layers are shown in the following **Table 1**.

Layer	Description
Business	The business logic of a company, for example, strategies for the material management or production planning from a perspective point of view.
Functional	Contains formal descriptions of functions, for example, process steps in a factory. Function-based logic like the processing and parametrization of machines by using the accessibility via Asset Administration Shell of Information Layer is related to this layer.
Information	The information layer provides process-related information in form of data (e.g., machines or products). Realization of an Asset Administration

	Shell can provide a structured and standardized representation in this layer.
Communication	Interconnection across different networks (IoT).
Integration	Connects physical assets to the virtual world in form of digitization, for example, sensors or PLC.
Asset	The physical asset in the sense of RAMI, e.g., a machine or product.

Table 1 Axis Layers of the RAMI4.0

2.2 IDS-RAM

The International Data Space Reference Architecture Model (IDS-RAM), shown in **Figure 2**, focuses on the generalization of concepts, functionality and overall processes. It follows common system architecture models and standards (such as ISO 420210) and uses a five-layer structure, involving stakeholders and different viewpoints at different levels of granularity. The general structure of the viewports and layers is shown in the following figure.

Figure 2 IDS-RAM general structure

2.3 IIRA

The Industrial Internet Reference Architecture (IIRA), shown in **Figure 3**, is based on the ISO/IEC/IEEE 42010:2011 standard to define its architecture framework. It is a specific architecture for IIoT systems across industrial sectors and classifies them into viewpoints along with their respective stakeholders.

The IIRA has a level of abstraction that excludes architectural elements whose evaluation requires specificities only available in concrete systems. Thus, it does not explicitly identify the model kind as a key construct of its framework, instead, it uses the concept loosely during the analysis of concerns in developing its representation. Also, it does not explicitly discuss certain architecture constructs, correspondence rules, correspondence and architecture rationale; it leaves them to the development of concrete architectures as needed.

In general, the IIRA identifies four viewpoints for its architecture:

- Business viewpoint
- Usage viewpoint
- Functional viewpoint
- Implementation viewpoint

Like the RAMI 4.0 model, the IIRA considers the lifecycle of the process in its architectural view. However, it differentiates into different application scopes, meaning industrial sectors. The viewpoints of the IIRA about their lifecycle and industrial sector is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Relationship between IIRA viewpoints, application scope and lifecycle

For the functional viewpoint, the IIRA frames the concerns related to the functional capabilities and structure of an IIoT system and its components. It decomposes a typical IIoT system into five functional domains:

- Control domain
- Operations domain
- Information Domain
- Application Domain
- Business Domain

The functional components of the functional domain focus on major system functions that are generally required to support generic IIoT usages and to realize generic IIoT system capabilities for business purpose. However, the IIRA also considers additional functions that are required for the major system to function. Furthermore, characteristics are considered that are required for the functions to perform correctly and not compromise their business purpose. These functional domains and their correlation to system characteristics as well as crosscutting functions are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 IIRA functional domains concerning the system characteristics and cross-cutting functions. Green arrows represent data /information flow, Grey decision flows, Red command/request flows

2.4 ISO/IEC 30141 IoT Reference Architecture

The IoT Reference architecture is specified in ISO/IEC 30141, as shown in **Figure 5**. Inside the model, there are different architecture views, namely:

- Functional view
- System deployment view
- Networking view
- Usage view
- Domain view

Based on these different views, a domain view of the system is shown in **Figure 5**. Next to the domain functions of User Domain, Operations & Management Domain, Application & Service Domain, Access & Communication domain, Sensing & Controlling Domain, and the Physical Entity domain, there are Cross-domain capabilities. These are Connectivity, PII Protection, Security, Resilience, Interoperability and Dynamic composition.

Due to its nature, the architecture is for the internet of things and not for the smart manufacturing nor multiagent domain specifically.

Figure 5 ISO 30414 IoT RA domain view

2.5 ADMARMS

The Axiomatic design of multiagent reconfigurable mechatronic system (ADMARMS) architecture [1], shown in Figure 6, was proposed by Farid and Ribeiro.

The architecture is based on several design principles to maximize the reconfiguration potential of a mechatronic system:

- Principle 1: Describe the agent architecture in terms of the production equipment that adds reconfigurability to the system.
- Principle 2: The multi-agent system must maintain a 1-1 relationship with the set of physical capabilities that exist on the shop floor.
- Principle 3: The agent architecture must respect the heterogeneity of capabilities found within the shop floor be they various types of transformation, transportation or storage processes.

- Principle 4: The agent architecture must reflect and support the physical aggregation of the objects that they represent.
- Principle 5: The agent architecture must explicitly model and consider that resources and processes are not always present in the system.
- Principle 6: The agent architecture must contain agent interactions along with the minimal set of possible interactions.
- Principle 7: Aside from the minimal set of physical interactions, the agent architecture should avoid introducing any further interactions (which may impose further constraints).
- Principle 8: Align agents' scope and boundaries with their corresponding physical resources.
- Principle 9: Production system information should be placed in the agent corresponding to the physical entity that it describes.
- Principle 10: The same reconfiguration process can require significantly different effort (measured in time, cost, energy...) depending on the method used to conduct the reconfiguration (and not just the reconfigured resources). The architecture should cater for the quantification of the system.

Figure 6 ADMARMS architecture and data model

2.6 Reference architecture of autonomous systems

A general reference architecture of autonomous systems that has been discussed in the context of agent-based systems was supposed by W. Wahlster, describing the features of autonomous systems and providing an overview of needed components. It is described in [2].

The reference architecture for autonomous systems, as shown in **Figure 7**, was developed by abstracting the architectures that have been used for autonomous systems in recent years. In the reference architecture, the requirements from different application areas are included and uniformly represented in an architecture. Within the framework of the reference architecture for autonomous systems, technological enablers (existing concepts of autonomous systems, internationally competitive technology modules or software tools) for autonomous systems are to be further developed. In doing so, the reference architecture is evaluated in the overall context of an ecosystem by considering the technological embedding of autonomous systems. Autonomous systems depend on many developments, such as 5G infrastructure or sensor technology. In addition, several autonomous systems together can again form an autonomous system, the autonomous factory. Since autonomous systems can differ in their granularity and still should act interconnected, aggregation mechanisms have also been considered.

The reference architecture focuses on the three essential functions of autonomous systems: sensors, Self-regulation, and actuators. With the help of sensor technology, the state of the environment is observed. Self-regulation and knowledge bases evaluate the observations and generate action plans, which are finally executed by the actuators. The actuator system thus changes the state of the environment to achieve the system's goal. This is repeated in further iterations until all goals of the autonomous system are achieved. In this process, the architecture requires a normative framework that always ensures the control capabilities of the operator of the system. This is done by communicating with the environment and with humans, which passes to the autonomous system other important information for its behaviour.

The mentioned knowledge bases are built up by automated modeling and are constantly adapted, corrected, or expanded throughout the life of the autonomous system. Episodic memory is included as long-term memory for important events and enables case-based reasoning and learning from experience. Also, a discourse memory stores the entire course of the system's communication with people and technical systems in the environment, so that references to previous events can be used at any time. Furthermore, the knowledgebases also contain a plan library and a model library. The plan library stores successfully executed plans that have led to the achievement of goals in problems frequently encountered. The model library is significant to the performance of the autonomous system and can be divided into different models, such as domain, task, collaboration, or user models. These libraries all lead to better

recognition and classification of situations to achieve a given goal faster together with other actors.

For cognitive information processing, the reference architecture consists of several components, which are controlled for self-regulation by different mechanisms. The components for perception and interpretation recognize the objects and situations and appropriate actuator schemes are activated or action planning is initiated. For learning and reasoning, machine learning is significant, because huge amounts of training data are used to compute very robust and compact models for accurate classifiers. Thus, sensory inputs can be directly translated to actuator outputs without any intermediate steps through end-to-end learning of deep neural networks. On the other hand, if more time is available but there is a lack of training data, the use of temporal and spatial inference techniques can be used in an AI to improve performance. In this case, statistical learning methods are extended by automatic reasoning. With the help of the planning of actions in an autonomous system, goal-oriented actions are to be selected automatically. For this purpose, the system contains a formal model of the environment, the available actions, and the target and boundary conditions, which enables it to simulate possible developments with the help of a planning algorithm. So, it is given a goal to which an action strategy is developed. On the opposite, in plan recognition, a goal is determined based on observing specific actions. This can be used to predict the behavior of other agents. For communication of the autonomous system with humans, AI methods are used to adapt the system more and more to human communication modalities. Users' speech, gestures, facial expressions, and glances are analyzed, and a virtual agent with humanoid behavior embodies the autonomous system as a dialogue partner. Based on secure communication, collaboration with humans and other autonomous systems as well as the environment is enabled. For this purpose, AI techniques can be used in the field of multi-agent systems. Based on assumptions about the knowledge, skills and experience of the agents involved, tasks are negotiated and optimally distributed.

To prevent the endangerment of people in the environment in the case of technical problems or complete failures, the reference architecture includes a technical fallback level. In this way, the autonomous system is supposed to enter a safe operating state via redundant mechatronic functions or radio-based remote controls, in which the autonomous additional functions are not used.

Also, in certain situations, it will be necessary to execute a transfer of control to the human when the autonomous system reaches the limits of its capabilities. For this reason, the reference architecture includes a bidirectional transfer of control between the human and the autonomous system. Therefore, interaction platforms (multimodal presentations) are considered, whereby

the cognitive state of the human is considered. A safe and smooth handover of control from the system is ensured by time and content planning (handover plan). In doing so, the autonomous systems are to be adapted more to the communication behavior of humans than vice versa and the human remains the foreman in the team with robots.

Figure 7 Reference architecture for autonomous systems, from [2]

3 MAS4AI High Level Structure Overview

The software and communication structure of the MAS4AI system is illustrated in **Figure 8**. The kernel of the Multi-Agent System is built by a Message-Based Middleware (MOM, e.g. Apache Kafka, Basyx, etc.) using industrial Internet-of-Things (IoT) web service technologies (e.g. based on HTTP, MQTT, AMQP, OWL-S). Furthermore, the MOM includes connectors to OPC-UA for real-time control of processes and a Gateway for connecting IoT and OPC-UA networks. The system is completely event-based incorporating a Publish-Subscribe mechanism. Autonomous Agents are utilizing several microservices, which are configured for specific applications. In contrast to the underlying services, the agents interact autonomously with other agents, have their memory, access to the Data Collection and can learn and adapt to the actual needs. Running agents in the network are discovered and registered (see A-Discovery, A-Registry) to provide them to other agents. The Agent Configuration & Execution service interprets the Agent Service Description of the registered Agents and matches required and provided agent services. Furthermore, new agents can be executed from the Agent Repository. Agents for Human-Machine-Interaction (HMI) and AI agents are operated on the Module/Physical Process level as well as on the Production Planning and Control level. The AI-on-demand Connector Agents interfaces with cloud services.

Figure 8 MAS4AI software and communication structure

4 Architecture Design principles

The design principles of the MAS4AI architecture are based on the principles shown in Figure 9. In this document, the focus is on Stage 1 and Stage 2. High design principles are defined first, which are followed by the architecture. These are the basis of a generalisable multi-agent reference architecture for manufacturing environments, with a particular focus on compatibility with the Industrie 4.0 reference architecture.

The architecture should be scalable and independent of the frameworks ultimately used (such as Jadex) for the multi-agent system itself. The reference to the assets used in production is important for general usability and for scaling. Such an asset is, as described in chapter 2, a value-added object in production, such as a robot. Agents can be assigned to it, but individual assets must not receive multiple conflicting instructions from a multi-agent system. A division into information and control flow is therefore necessary. Similarly, everyone-with-everyone communication is to be avoided in a production environment, as the number of participants can potentially become too high to support such communication. To provide this abstraction and scalability, holons (in chapter 5) are proposed as a solution. The protocols used and the high-level architecture developed will then be further defined in Stage 2 with a specific modelling language, but the actual elaboration will take place in the following Work Packages. The reference architecture created in this way is described in Chapter 5 with its components, protocols and interactions, providing the conceptual design for further research in the work packages of the MAS4AI project.

Figure 9 System Design Process. Source: [1]

The MAS4AI Reference Architecture, following the described State-of-the-Art Reference Architectures in the scope of Industrie 4.0 will be introduced in this section. The Architecture is described as a RAMI-integrated holonic approach that follows the asset-based view of I4.0 components with Asset Administration and the classification of several agent types a MAS can have in production environments. The MAS4AI Reference Architecture presents a framework-independent approach for MAS but defines requirements and interfaces to bring the approach into already existing MAS frameworks.

4.1 Design approaches

First, the meaning and benefits of the holonic approach will be introduced in this section. A classification into RAMI will be done and the elements and interfaces of such an holonic system will be shown.

4.1.1 Holons, agents and assets

A holon is an autonomous, intelligent and cooperative building block of a manufacturing system, which provides transformation, transportation and other industrial tasks [14]. Holon represents a very tight integration of physical and computation parts and in that sense, it has a direct analogy to a more recent concept of cyber-physical production system (CPPS). Holonic manufacturing systems can realize a very robust and flexible manufacturing environment. They consist of holons, which are viewed as atomic concepts and organized in a hierarchy, which is called holarchy. Because agents and holons share many concepts, MAS can be a very good candidate to realize an HMS. Though, strictly speaking, holons and agents are not the same, in recent years the border between the two paradigms has blurred. In the project we use these two concepts interchangeably, meaning a holonic agent.

We define a holon as an abstraction element for the MAS4AI Multiagent system. A holon follows the definition for assets, as it can contain one or multiple assets (both hardware assets, such as sensors, or software assets, such as ERP software) and combines it with an I4.0 compatible asset administration shell (AAS). However, a distinction lies in the combination of agents with an asset.

A Holon can be perceived as part of a higher system composition, which follows the same approach as the holon itself. A fractal system design in which a holon can be seen as its unit, but also can be part of another system unit with its composition, can be used to match the requirements of modular and scalable production systems. A fractal approach is schematically shown on **Figure 11**.

In our system, an agent, or multiple agents, can be attached to (communicate with) an asset over an AAS that in turn is linked to this asset. An agent can have an interface in form of an AAS to communicate/interact with an I4.0 Asset in a structural way. This agent itself also has an Agent Service Description (ASD), which it uses to be compatible with AAS following the I4.0 definition. Through this interface an agent can be dynamically configured. **Figure 10** shows the relation between an asset, agents and a holon.

Figure 10 Relation between Asset and Holon

This ASD serves as an abstraction level between the agent and the AAS. It is to be discussed whether this ASD will be its own “AAS” specific for agents, or if it will be part of the agent itself. It must rather also be discussed, for which cases an ASD should be used, for example:

- If Agents of an agent framework are communicating with similar agents of the same framework.
- If Agents of an agent framework are communicating with agents of different frameworks or other global/local interfaces of a system or also I4.0 Assets.

The ASD is similar to an AAS, however it might differ in the exact contents. Plan is it to design it as close to the AAs as possible and eventually merge them once the specifics are clear.

The AAS Repository of the MAS4AI System Architecture fulfils the requirements to organize current available I4.0 Assets with their digital representation (and interface) in form of the AAS. If the ASD concept is equal or different to the AAS concept, this will have an impact on the architectures part of the AAS Repository, so there will be a need to set up an ASD Repository or to integrate this concept into the AAS Repository (if similar).

Both the AAS of the Asset, as well as (the ASD of) the agent will be part of the overall “holon”, which represents an asset with its AAS and thus follows the definition of industry 4.0 components. This industry 4.0 component itself can be part of another holon.

Figure 11 Fractal approach of an holon

The advantage of this approach lies in the flexibility of the definition of an asset, especially in the higher hierarchy layers of the factory. While in the lower layers, the mapping between agent and (Hardware-) asset might be almost 1:1, in the higher levels – where assets can again contain multiple assets of lower hierarchy layers – this mapping is not as clear. Especially when agents do not describe assets but are an asset. This holonic approach gives the flexibility of considering both agents and non-agent assets while being consistent with the definition of industry 4.0 components.

Figure 12 Exemplary setup of a Holon

In order to be compatible with the I4.0 architecture and the concept of AAS, ASD can be defined as a standardized AAS submodel (using standard submodel elements).

4.1.2 A design approach to let agents interact with an Asset Administration Shell

There are several approaches to how agents could use a service or an AAS. The difference can be pointed up by using MAS frameworks, for example, the MAS Janus SARL, which supports holons and fractal agents' structures and interfaces to interact with an environment that does not consist only of agent system elements. In the following figure, the design options of such a framework to interact with system elements are pointed up.

The first option is to interact directly with another software element without AAS (e.g., an interface to a machine learning program). The second option is to interact with system elements that have a passive AAS (which can be deployed as a separate structure-giving part in an external system like cloud, or that is directly be integrated into an I4.0 Asset as own AAS-compliant interface definition, e.g., following the OPC UA AAS Companion Specification). In this case, an OPC UA server could provide the AAS interface that can be accessed by agents.

Figure 13 Interfaces of the Holon

Another approach, which follows more the concept of the active AAS is, to integrate the agents also in an I4.0 Asset, which expand the structure and behaviour of the asset and describe the agents' capabilities and properties in the same way as an Asset with an own agent related AAS submodel.

Figure 14 Integration of MAS frameworks within the architecture

These design aspects for passive and active AAS with the need for AAS for agents lead to the holonic approach. An asset thereby could also be managed by its agent system and follows the idea of a fractal system (MAS system in a MAS system), it has an AAS and parts to interact with suitable agents in the MAS system context.

4.2 Holonic Approach for MAS4AI

4.2.1 Classification of the holonic approach in RAMI

A holonic manufacturing system (HMS) can be seen as a system that consists of several own systems, following a fractal approach. The holonic agents' concept can also be represented partly in the RAMI 4.0 across the axis of hierarchy levels, so between the enterprise and field device level, it follows the ISA-95 standard. The hierarchy levels are highlighted in Figure 15.

Figure 15: RAMI 4.0 Hierarchy Levels for static classified Holons

4.2.2 Static classified and dynamic classified Holons

Holons can be build up in various manners, whereas the holonic context plays an important role. We divide between two holonic types, underlining the aspect that static and dynamic classified holons could both enable a dynamic behaviour:

- Static classified Holons

A static classified holon represents a part of a production system, which can be consist of various assets and agents. Such holons follow predefined order criteria, for example, the

hierarchy levels of RAMI. A holon thus can be a factory, consisting of several stations that can be seen as own holons.

Figure 16: Predefined static classified holons

- **Dynamic classified Holons**

A dynamic classified holon can be built, if two static classified holons of the same level interact with each other to solve a problem or to collect data about a production system. In this case, a new dynamic holon for this interaction can be build up. This dynamic holon does not follow a predefined order criterion but uses it to build up its context with several system elements, e.g., I4.0 components and agents. Based on the holonic approach, these selected system elements can also be represented by their own holons. Due to the expectable complexity of such holons, dynamic holons only can be built from two static defined ones.

Figure 17: Dynamic classified holons during interaction

4.2.3 Structure and Self-Description of a MAS4AI-Holon

A holon can be built up from many holons with its systems, containing I4.0 components and/or agent systems. The smallest entity of a holon is at least one part of a MAS4AI-System, for example, a simple agent or a single active asset. This definition is necessary because, during the build-up of dynamic holons, other holons that need to interact with other holons to solve a problem and to reach a goal does not need information about the structure of the interaction partner holon, that can consist of many I4.0 components and agents. The probability to find a holon that only has one system element is higher at a lower level of a static classified holon, but it is not a sufficient condition. This offers the possibility to implement its hardware-near MAS-frameworks with this concept, representing its functionality as its holon for higher-level holonic systems and other MAS-framework.

Holons in the MAS4AI architecture have an own AAS as an interface to interact with other holons. The holonic AAS can consist of several AAS submodels, like the AAS of an asset. A holon can also inherit various agents, which are provided from a MAS-Framework. Agents inside such a holon have interactions with a message-based interaction pattern.

Each agent in a holonic context will provide its own agent service description (ASD) as part of the self-description of the agent's service. In context to the holonic approach, where each holon provides an interface in form of an AAS, it is intended to research if the ASD can be provided and configured by the holon AAS as its submodels. It is possible, that several agent types and their services can be described in the way of an ASD and that this part of the description will lead to own submodels of the holons AAS. ASD as a concept to let agents interact in their environment,

e.g., defined frameworks like Jade, Jadex or similar and to define the agents' services for agent interaction in the MAS4AI system. It is intended to research if the concept of the AAS can fulfil the requirements of the ASD, following the presented holonic approach. In this case, agents could be described and configured (towards the aims of WP2) like an AAS, with an identifier, semantic references to ontologies, and related submodels for the agent interaction and their behaviour. With this reference, it could be possible to identify the several agent types (e.g., resource agent, product agent).

An overview of this concept can be found in the next figure:

Figure 18: Interface and Elements of an MAS4AI-Holon

4.2.4 Control and Information Flow in the holonic context

Each holon will also contain a "Coalition"-Agent in Form of a Supervisor Agent. This Agent will take part if there is a control flow to reach a goal, e.g. if two machines are interacting and want to exchange a product a new dynamic classified holon will be created. The Coalition-Agents takes manner to control available subsystems that also could be controlled by corresponding agents themselves in lower level holons. This agent takes also control, that the static classified holonic subparts of his holon are not part of another dynamic classified holon. In the case of hardware controlling content, it should be avoided for example, that a gripper could be part of a control flow of two transport units that want to access it at the same time. If this case occurs, then the requests could be queued by the interaction protocol dispatcher, following the check if the requested context of the call is still valid. This agent controls the interactions of the "Actuator"-related part of the autonomous reference architecture from W. Wahlster in a useful way.

Each holon can also contain a Data Management-Agent. This agent takes a manner that information can be collected, e.g., from assets (in form of software or hardware), preprocessed and stored. Unlike the Coalition-Agent, the Data Management-Agent can fulfil its tasks as part of many dynamic holons, if the data collection does not change the data context of these. For example, it should be possible, that many holons want to collect similar data from a production machine (e.g., if errors occur). In this case, the Data Management-Agent can grant access to the data collection of this asset and provide similar data collecting requests and whole datasets, if they are already collected, also for other holonic agents. This can be done in the form of data exchange, but also in form of references to data pools (e.g., if Apache Kafka is used). The Data Management-Agent can be linked to a local or global Knowledgebase in the agent environment. It is possible, that each agent contains an own Knowledgebase, but also can grant access to a more globally stored Knowledgebase. This agent controls the interactions of the "Sensor"-related part of the autonomous reference architecture from W. Wahlster in a useful way. If I4.0 assets with their own AAS and related submodels can be found in the holon, this agent can access necessary passive AAS with their submodels. They can also solve information requests from other agents, e.g., Machine Learning-Agents.

The information flow inside a holon can be explained in the example, visualized in the following figure. A production module, represented with a holon that consists of various agents and related AAS, in this case a Pick and Place-Unit and a LED-Unit, gets first a request for the Pick and Place-Skill from a transport unit to exchange a product on the shopfloor by using I4.0 language. This asset consists of two assets, a gripper and a camera. The coalition agent can fulfil this request due to available agents for this aim and no existing control-flow context of this asset. The Pick and Place-Unit with the Gripper and the Camera are now in the control flow context of

the Transport Unit. The coalition agent can initiate an acknowledgement to the transport unit, the context is active until the request is fulfilled.

A second request presents the importance of the management to control requests. If another holon, e.g., a Quality-Agent, requests the skill to take a picture, this request will be checked by the coalition agent. It is possible for the holon in general to provide the requested picture, but the agent with related asset is currently in another control flow context. To avoid unexpected system behavior if two systems want to execute skills of the same assets, the coalition agent can not acknowledge the request and is informing the Quality-Agent that the request is denied. Another possibility than to deny the request is to check, if it can be queued. Therefore, it must be ensured that the request is still valid, if the request can be fulfilled.

The benefit of this approach can be pointed up in another request from a Safety-Agent, which observed the control flow context of the Transport-Unit regarding the Pick and Place-Unit of the production module. The agent sends the request to initiate a warn-signal on the shopfloor during the process of exchanging the product between the production module and the transport unit. The coalition agent checks the request, and it can be fulfilled by activating the LEDs of the production module. The LED as asset is currently not in a control flow context and a new control flow context for the Safety-Agents request can be granted with a acknowledge.

Figure 19 Holon Information flow

To decide about which control context is possible with available agents and assets is a very important decision which should be investigated in the MAS4AI approach. A main benefit of the holonic approach that decides about control flow contexts is to check current available contexts and to execute skills in parallel. This could be an advantage to a completely microservice-based system architecture, because higher-level context classes of such a architecture are just locking the complete context object during a request.

4.2.5 Registry and Discovery of Assets and Agents

Important system element for finding Assets in an I4.0 environment with the AAS is a Registry-Element and a Discovery-Element. With a registry element, all existing assets with their machine skills can be stored in form of an AAS, e.g., in a database, to make them available for control software. In the case of a MAS, the registry of assets with their AAS can also be used for belonging agents of the MAS. Here, the question of the syntax and structure of the agent's self-description is very important and can be compared with the requirements to discover suitable assets. If the agents can fulfil also the requirement of self-description in form of an ASD or towards an AAS, then these agents should also be considered in the Registry and Discovery-Process.

Implications to elements of the MAS4AI System architecture can be seen in discovery and registry if the agents will have an AAS and/or an ASD. If the evaluation results will show that the

AAS-concept can be used for an ASD and the results are suitable with the AAS Metamodel concept, then the Discovery / Registry Element of the architecture should be the same entity for both, and no differentiation regarding a new system element is needed. In this case, the AAS can be used for Assets like Modules and Agents and Holons.

If this concept can be applied to the architecture, then it would be possible to define patterns for the agent/holon AAS which can be implemented in different MAS frameworks to meet the MAS4AI standard. With this pattern, it should be possible to enable agents of frameworks to use such Registries and the Discovery mechanism. Discovery/Registry element can be seen equivalent to the existing Directory Facilitator or Yellow Pages pattern from the MAS community.

Regarding the functionality, OPC UA Servers with implemented AAS Companion Specification can meet the requirements of AAS on the one hand and provide a mechanism for discovery (LDS – Local Discovery Server) and server registry. Another possibility for integration of these system elements could be the usage of the Open-Source BaSyx-Middleware of the BaSys 4.0 and BaSys 4.2 research project, which provides Registry and Discovery of AAS.

In terms of the holonic approach, these components can also host the AAS of holons (e.g., static holons can be stored in this registry). Each holon with integrated agents should have at least a local registry for its assets and agents to ensure reliability and resilience between them. The system element of registry and discovery should also be available for holons on the same static holon level (as part of a higher holon), so the possibility to interact with other agents is granted.

4.3 Interaction Protocols

4.3.1 Industry 4.0 Interactions Model

An interactions model of Industry 4.0 (I4.0) components follows a simple classification of interactions between components, introduced in [4], and divides I4.0 components on vertically and horizontally interacting systems. Vertically interacting systems can be described by the "Use and Observe" model. An "upper" component interacts with a "lower" component through the function calls ("uses" it) and should know its counterpart. The "lower" one makes no assumptions about the "upper layer" and can communicate through events (being "observed"). This type of interactions builds hierarchically composed and tightly coupled systems. Horizontal interactions can also be called "Mutual Hinting" and are described by protocols. Each partner "hints" the others about its state-change through specific events so the others can act accordingly. These interactions are stateful, nondeterministic and asynchronous. They build loosely coupled systems that cooperatively interact with each other.

The interaction model is shown in **Figure 20**, where two components interact “horizontally” with each other, using the I4.0 language, and “vertically” with the physical world using functions and events. The submodels form the passive part of the I4.0 component’s administration shell and the vocabulary for the I4.0 language. The interactions manager with the set of the protocols and the decisions algorithms build the active part of the AAS.

Figure 20 Interactions between I4.0 components (adapted from [5] and [6]).

One way to design interactions is to use a set of predefined interaction protocols. Agents can engage in meaningful conversation with other agents by following the known protocol that relates to each other’s roles in the interaction. This idea is used in the concept of the I4.0 language, described in the next section.

4.3.2 Language 4.0 and Semantic Interaction Protocol

The I4.0 language was elaborated by the technical committee "Semantics and Interaction for I4.0 Components" of the VDI/VDE Association for Measurement and Automation Technology [10] and are supposed to realize complex interactions between I4.0 components. It defines a set of rules for building up data elements, used in its messages, the structure of these messages, and the semantic interaction protocols to organize the message sequences to the meaningful dialogues. The language is completely independent of the type of communication, meaning that an application forms the I4.0 language compliant messages, packs them into the service data units as useful data and exchanges them using the services, provided by the concrete

communications technology. The concept of the I4.0 language is shown schematically on Figure 20.

Figure 21. I4.0 Language Concept

Part 1 of the guideline VDI 2193 [7] defines the vocabulary and the message structure of the I4.0 language, while part 2 [8] (and future parts) the semantic interaction protocols or the structural principles and the rules for the dialogues between I4.0 components. These rules though incomplete, but precise, and serve as common knowledge between the interacting parties to support the achievement of their interaction goal [9].

The vocabulary of the I4.0 language consists of the standardized properties in a machine-processable data format, according to IEC61360. These properties are essentially the words of the I4.0 language.

Further, the guideline standardizes the structure of the messages, being used in message-based communications between I.4 components. This is required to provide a common

understanding and proper processing of the messages among all the participants of I4.0 communications.

The semantic interaction protocols form the last part of the I4.0 language. They assure the proper sequence of the messages, needed for meaningful and successful conversation between I4.0 components. Currently, only one semantic interaction protocol was described in the guideline, namely the “bidding procedure”, which is based on the contract network protocol. Its goal is to establish legally binding negotiation between I4.0 components across company boundaries. In [12] a “skill execution” semantic interaction protocol was introduced. Its goal is to establish cooperation between I4.0 components, a skill-provider and a skill-requester, in the form of an automated “skill execution” procedure. This type of interaction protocol follows a skill-based approach and enables all the agents to use the other agents’ functionalities, abstracted as skills, consistently and almost autonomously.

It is also worth mentioning that the concept of I4.0 language takes a lot of its ideas from the FIPA AIPS, described in the previous section. This makes it feasible to integrate both approaches.

The guideline VDI 2193-1 defines the vocabulary and the structure of the I4.0 language messages to enable their correct processing by interacting with partners; see . The message consists of a frame and a data-part, which is called “InteractionsElements”. The frame has a relatively fixed structure with some optional elements in it. It serves mainly for identification purposes with different level of granularity. The data part is optional and carries all information, which is relevant for successful interaction. Although the structure of the data part is not fixed, the elements are strictly defined. They are constrained to submodel elements and references to other submodels. Detailed information on the I4.0 language message structure can be found in [10, 6].

Figure 22 I4.0 language message structure

The type element of the message is mandatory and very important to establish a meaningful conversation between the interaction participants. It defined the purpose of interaction as communicative speech acts; see 1.1.1. **Table 2** shows some examples of such purposes.

Type	The action of the sender/receiver
General status	
Consent	I will execute the function you requested.
Refusal	I refuse to execute the function you requested.
Not understand	I did not understand what you want me to do
Contract initiation	
Call for proposals	Please send me offers for the following call for proposals.
Offer	I offer to execute this offer.

Table 2 List of purposes (Types) as communicative speech acts (excerpt from [6])

MAS represent a powerful model to solve distributed computation problems, including being able to adapt their operation in open and dynamic environments in which the content and workload are continuously changing. MAS can utilize other agents for cooperative distributed problem solving when individual agents don't wish to or can't perform tasks within certain constraints or don't have the competency to perform tasks by themselves. Agents can cooperate by using an Agent Communication Language (ACL) to support the sharing of a rich agreed

understanding concerning the semantics of the message content and the semantics of the communication context of the message content.

The semantics of the content typically defines shared information and tasks with respect to some domain such as a specific service or application domain. The semantics of the communication context explicitly defines relationships between a particular message concerning a context such as a sender agent’s current workflow, an agreed interaction protocol, goals and plans, or for a receiving agent’s beliefs, desires, and intentions. Agents can be designed to operate more competitively in marketplaces than cooperatively so that agents can select services from a variety of other agents that best fit the constraints in meeting their goals.

4.4 Specific Agent Roles in the Architecture

4.5 Patterns

To enable the holonic approach for MAS4AI functionality, it is intended to define and build up reference patterns, which can be implemented for specific MAS frameworks. The patterns are described as framework-independent and can be implemented.

Pattern	Description	Has Part	Part of
Static holon	<p>Pattern for static holons, suitable to the MAS4AI approach. The main object, representing the current MAS. Contains all agents and interface to assets. This object represents the entry for all lower-level static holons and is responsible for the building and inheritance of lower-level holons. This holon also is responsible for the creation and destruction of agents in its context.</p> <p>Parametrization of inherited agents intended by using the holonic AAS.</p>	<p>Registry Discovery Knowledge Base Cloud- Connector Low-Level Holon Configured Agents Coalition Agent Data Coll. Agent AAS</p>	<p>Other static holons (same level) Higher Holons</p>
Dynamic holon	The pattern of a dynamic holon to use the ACL for interaction.	<p>One or many valid static holons of the same level. AAS</p>	Static holon with higher level.

ACL	Pattern to ensure agents communication by using an ACL, for example in form of the I4.0 language.	-	Dynamic Holons
AAS	Pattern to connect AAS to Agents (from lower level static holons or assets)	-	Static holon Agent-Types
Registry	Pattern for software adapter with generic interface description to registry components.		Static holon
Discovery	Pattern for software adapter with generic interface description to registry components.		Static holon
Gateway	Pattern for software adapter with generic interface description for translation.	AAS	Static holon
Cloud Connector	Pattern for software adapter with generic interface description for cloud services, e.g., GAIA X-Environment.	AAS	Static holon
HMI/HMC	Pattern for HMI / HMC. Contains the ability to access holons with a higher priority than other system agents. Enables monitoring, data collection and override of the system behaviour.	AAS	Holons
Agent-Types	Contains several agent types, like planning agents, energy agents etc. E.g., special agents for Toolchain support, like Deployment Agents.	AAS	Holons

Table 3 Interaction patterns

5 MAS4AI Reference Architecture

In this section the MAS4AI reference architecture will be defined formally using UML diagrams.

5.1 Basic building blocks of the MAS4AI architecture.

Figure 24 shows a component diagram of the I4.0 CPPS, which consists of I4.0 components, such as I4.0 CPPM, I4.0 holon and I4.0 agent. We use here the definition of the I4.0 component, which is defined as an asset with its asset administration shell, and map it in the same manner to the holon and the agent. In general a system in MAS4AI consists of assets, agents and holons. When they get their standard digital representation in form of the AAS, they become I4.0 components and interact with each other in the I4.0 environment. Figure 24 shows a I4.0 Cyber-Physical Production System (CPPS) that is defined as an aggregation of human resources (not shown), I4.0 Cyber-Physical Production Modules (CPPMs), but also holons and agents. An agent as well as holon can be treated also as assets and be given the standardized description in the form of AAS. Equipped with the AASs they become I4.0 components.

Figure 24 Holon, Agent and Asset in the Industrie 4.0 Environment

5.2 Aggregation of Holonic Agents

Structuring agents in hierarchies lowers the system complexity and make it more predictable and understandable. The related holons can be clustered together to form a high-order holon with its own identity. The aggregation here can be not only a tree-like, but holons can belong to

multiple aggregations. Figure 25 shows the holon aggregation for the factory source holons. It resembles the factory hierarchy, typical for manufacturing, but the hierarchy here is not static and one holon can simultaneously be part of several other holons, e.g. a device holon can be a part of a station holon and a part of a work center holon.

Figure 25 Aggregation of the Factory Resource Holons

5.3 MAS4AI Holonic Resource Agent Architecture

Figure 26 shows the class diagram of the MAS4AI holonic resource agent architecture. At the bottom of the diagram different assets' classes are shown such as a CPPM, a robot and a conveyor. Each of them provides one or more production skills that represent the module's functionalities with the standardized interface. The agents can use these skills through the common known interface. For example, the Agent CPPM uses two skills from two different modules – the CPPM skill and the PickAndPlace skill. The Agent Transport Module uses the Transport skill. When an agent uses a production module skill it registers it as its property. It can use it to build more complex behaviours or just provide it to the other agents. The agents create their complex behaviours as a coordination of different skills. A behaviour can be defined as an interface, e.g. a Default Process Behaviour interface or a Manufacturing Behaviour interface on the class diagram. These interfaces define which skills are needed to complete some task. Different formal models can be used to define the dynamics of the agents' behaviours, such as Finite State Machines (FSMs), Petri Nets (PN) or Behaviour Trees (BT). On the class diagram the agents' classes implement the behaviour interfaces. The holonic agent that represents a Production Line aggregates two other agents, namely, the CPPM agent and the Transport Modul agent.

Figure 26 MAS4AI Holonic Agent's Architecture

5.4 Dynamic Behaviour Building in the Aggregated Resource Holon

Figure 27 shows a block diagram that describes, how the complex behaviours for the resource holons can be built dynamically. It builds upon the concepts, presented in [11], and adds the skills and the agents. This can be used from coordinating other agents or holons by building flexible hierarchies to achieve a goal. The diagram shows an I4.0 CPPM that consists of an asset and its cyber representation in form of the AAS. It also has its native cyber layer with a set of skills. The skills can be treated as industrial services with well-defined and standardized interface. The skills

need to be orchestrated to achieve some useful effect in the production system. This can be done by the behaviour holon, which is a part of the resource holon, and is responsible for the skills orchestration in a flexible and robust way. It consists of a behaviour builder, behaviour monitor and behaviour executor agents. The behaviour builder uses some of the formal models, which are used for coordination tasks, e.g. Finite State Machines (FSMs), Petri Nets (PN) or Behaviour Trees (BT), to dynamically generate the executable code for the behaviour executor. It uses the high-level specification of the process from the Product Holon.

Figure 27 Dynamic building of the Resource Holon behaviour

5.5 Specializations of Holonic Agents

This section describes three class diagrams that show specialisations of the main agents types of the MAS4AI architecture. Specialisation is used to differentiate between different kinds of the same general type of an agent and in the same time to preserve some common properties of these agents.

5.5.1 Resource Agent Specialization

Figure 28 shows the specialization of the MAS4AI holonic resource agents. There 3 main classes of the resource agents: production module agent, transport agent and equipment agent. Production module agent can be called transformers, because they represent the machines,

which transform materials to the sub- or final products. Transport agents represent all kinds of transporters. They do not transform anything, but move the goods from one place to another. The equipment agents represent devices, which provide functionalities different from product transformation and transportation, e.g. quality inspection and safety control. Here the difference to the production and transport agents is subtle. For example, a robot being a universal tool can transform parts, e.g. by milling, or move them.

Figure 28 Specialization of Resource Holonic Agents

5.5.2 Information Agent Specialization

Figure 29 shows the class diagram for the specialization of the information agent. We defined three main types of the information agent: data collection agent, HMI agent and energy agent. The goal of the data collection agents is gather the relevant data, aggregate it and publish for the further usage by other agents. For that the Kafka middleware will be used. The goal of the HMI agent is to interact with the operators to support their decisions and enable the human-oriented manufacturing. The primary goal on the information energy agent is to gather and handle the energy data. These agents will be a part of the energy holons that will optimize the energy consumption/generation of the CPPS.

Figure 29 Specialization of Information Holonic Agents

5.5.3 Infrastructure Agent Specialization

The main goal of the infrastructure agents is to enable the work of other agents in the MAS. Figure 30 shows the class diagram of the infrastructure agents: an Agent Management System (AMS), a Directory Facilitator (DF), a Message Transport System (MTF) and a Communication Agent. They will be described in the following section.

Figure 30 Specialization of Infrastructure Agents

5.6 MAS Infrastructure agents

To enable the stable work of a MAS FIPA standard defines several system’s component for providing vital administrative functions. These components can also be realized as holonic agents. Figure 31 shows a block diagram of the MAS infrastructure.

Figure 31 MAS infrastructure

5.6.1 Agent Management System

FIPA standard defines an Agent Management System (AMS) as a mandatory component of every agent system. It provides a supervisory control over the use of the platform. It provides so called white pages services to the agents. It holds the repository of the agent's addresses and each agent must register itself with the AMS to get the valid agent's ID.

5.6.2 Directory Facilitator

A Directory Facilitator (DF) provides yellow pages services to the other agents. Agents register their services with the DF and can find out what services are provided by the other agents. In our project with use the more abstract term capability to describe a possible functionality of an entity, i.e. an intelligent agent. The holonic agents register their capabilities with the DF agent.

5.6.3 Message Transport System

A Message Transport System (MTS) is used to provide the physical message transfer between the agents withing a MAS or between several MASs. For the inter-MAS communication the internal MTS of the framework can be used. For the external communication it is proposed to use the communication holon and an open standard communication middleware, e.g. Kafka. For the message structure an I4.0 Language [10] is to be used.

5.6.4 Communication Holon

A communication holon is used as a gateway and provides the transparent communication services to the agents of the MAS. **Figure 32** shows a block diagram of two MASs that communicate with each other with the help of the communication holons and an external middleware, e.g. Kafka. The details of this setup as well as the structure of the communication holon will be described in the following work packages.

Figure 32 Two MAS runtimes communicate through an external middleware

5.7 Component diagram of holon interfaces

Figure 33 shows, how the agents in the MAS4AI system can connect to the external world. To connect to the other I4.0 components they use the asset administration shells as a standardized interface. The first possibility is to use an AAS middleware, e.g. the Basyx, which is used to provide services for the asset administration shells. It connects every asset in the system, be it hardware or software entity, to its AAS and establishes a REST-based web-interface to it. In this case, an agent uses the REST interface to connect to the CPPM’s AAS, which with the help of the Basyx gets access the CPPM. Another possibility is to use the module’s AAS directly, without the middleware, and use for it an OPCUA interface. In that case the AAS runs on the CPPM and

supports OPCUA AAS model. An agent can also use some non-standard interface, e.g. REST API, to connect to some backend service.

Figure 33 Holonic Agent's Interfaces

5.8 Interactions between Product Holon and Resource Holon

The sequence diagram on **Figure 34** shows the product agent and the holonic resource agent interact with each other and with the Product AAS to complete some production task. The product AAS provides of the necessary information on how to produce a product, i.e. information on the required production steps, capabilities, parameters, pre- and post- conditions. The product agent coordinates its actions with Product AAS and then interacts with the resource agent to request and parametrize the required skills, which are called on the particular CPPM.

Figure 34 Interaction between the product agent, the product AAS and the holonic resource agent

6 Further steps

In further steps, the components of the MAS4AI architecture described in this document must be developed and tested. This includes the functional creation of the components as well as possibilities to actively implement them in a system, e.g. by designing graphical user interfaces.

The architecture itself must of course also be tested for its suitability in the production context. It must be ensured that the architecture is suitable for the implementation of multi-agent systems in small, less automated as well as very large shop floors. The selection of suitable frameworks is just as much a part of this as the provision of templates for agents and holons and the precise elaboration of agents such as the Coalition Agent.

7 Conclusion

This deliverable describes the generic reference architecture that will be implemented in the MAS4AI project for the implementation of multi-agent systems in the use cases. This reference architecture is synchronous with the RAMI4.0 architecture and independent of the framework used. The architecture is based on a holonic approach to consider the complexity of a production system in a multi-agent approach. In this, a distinction is made between an information flow and a control flow.

In addition, the concept of an Agent Service Description (ASD) is introduced. This serves to make the agents quicker to use and easier to create, and it can also be used to parameterise the agent in the system. The ASD is strongly oriented towards the Asset Administration Shell (AAS) and can be represented as a partial model. A further approximation to the AAS will be examined in the further course of the project.

In the further course of the project, the components of the architecture described in this document, such as the ASD and the registry, must be developed. Then the developed reference architecture can be tested for its general suitability for use in production using a prototype implementation.

In summary, a reference architecture for multi-agent systems in the production context was developed in D1.3 that is compatible with existing definitions of the Reference Architecture for Industry 4.0 (RAMI4.0).

8 Literature

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